

Condensed Heterocyclic Systems. Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activities of Thiazolo[3',2':2,3][1,2,4]-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles and Isomeric Thiazolo-[2',3':3,4][1,2,4]triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles

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6-Chloro-5*H*-2,3-dihydro[1,2,4]triazino[5,6-*b*]indole-3-thione (2) on condensation with α -haloketones gives 5*H*-3-arylmethylthio-6-chloro[1,2,4]triazino[5,6-*b*]indole hydrohalides (3) which on PPA-catalysed cyclisation furnish 3-aryl-9-chlorothiazolo-[3',2':2,3][1,2,4]triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles (4) and not the angular isomeric 1-aryl-9-chlorothiazolo[2',3':3,4][1,2,4]triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles (6). The unequivocal synthesis of 6 has also been accomplished. The antibacterial and antifungal activities of some of the compounds have been evaluated.

In continuation to our earlier studies¹⁻⁵ on the orientation of cyclisation in the reaction of unsymmetrical mercaptoazoles with bifunctional compounds, we report herein the results of our study on the reaction of unsymmetrical azine (mercaptoindoletriazine) with α -haloketones.

6-Chloro-5*H*-2,3-dihydro[1,2,4]triazino[5,6-*b*]indole-3-thione (2), obtained by the condensation of 7-chloroisatin with thiosemicarbazide followed by the cyclisation of the intermediate 7-chloroisatin-3-thiosemicarbazone (1) with alkali, when condensed with α -haloketones gave 5*H*-3-arylmethylthio-6-chloro[1,2,4]triazino[5,6-*b*]indole hydrohalides (3*a-d*). The ketones (3*a-d*) being unsymmetrical, on cyclisation with PPA were expected to yield 3-aryl-9-chlorothiazolo[3',2':2,3][1,2,4]triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles (4*a-d*) or 1-aryl-9-chloro-thiazolo[2',3':3,4][1,2,4]triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles (6*a-e*) or both depending upon the mode of cyclisation. However, cyclisation of 3 gave a single product (tlc) and the formation of the cyclic product was confirmed by ir and nmr spectral data. The ketones (3*a-d*) exhibited a band at 1670-1700 cm⁻¹ (C=O), whereas the absence of this band in the ir spectrum of 4*a-d* showed the absence of carbonyl group, thereby suggesting the cyclic structure for 4. The signal at δ 7.80 (1H, s, C₂-H) in the pmr spectrum of 4*a* corroborated the cyclic structure. However, the spectral data were not of much help in deciding either the linear structure (4) or the angular structure (6) for the product.

The mode of cyclisation in 3 will be governed by the stability of the cyclic transition state (7 or 8). In structure 3, N-4 being more nucleophilic than N-2 (as N-2 is attached to N-1) will attack the carbonyl carbon of the ketone moiety giving 7. There exists a steric repulsion between NH of the

pyrrole ring and aryl moiety of the ketosulphide chain in 7 and this crowding would render the transition state 7 completely unstable, thus, the initially formed intermediate (7) being energetically more stable, opens up and closes at N-2 to give energetically less active intermediate 8 in which there would be no such steric crowding. The intermediate 8 finally undergoes prototropic change followed by loss of a water molecule to give 4 (Scheme 1).

The unequivocal synthesis of the angular isomer (6) was achieved by condensing 7-chloroisatin-3-thiosemicarbazone (1) with α -haloketones followed by cyclisation of the resulting 7-chloro-isatin-3-(4-aryl-2-thiazolyl)hydrazone hydrohalides (5*a-e*) with POCl₃ to furnish 1-aryl-9-chlorothiazolo-[2',3':3,4][1,2,4]triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles (6*a-e*). The amide carbonyl absorption, observed at 1670-1690 cm⁻¹ (5*a-e*), was found to be absent in the ir spectra of 6*a-e*. The pmr spectra (see experimental) corroborated the cyclic structure for 6.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Tlc was performed on silica gel plates using acetone-benzene (1:3) as irrigant. Ir spectra were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) instruments downfield from TMS.

7-Chloroisatin-3-thiosemicarbazone (1): A mixture containing boiling solutions of 7-chloroisatin (9.0 g, 0.05 mol) in acetic acid (80 ml) and thiosemicarbazide (5.0 g, 0.055 mol) in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) was refluxed on a heating mantle for 0.5 h. The brown coloured solid separated during heating

Scheme 1. Reagents : (i) KOH, (ii) and (iv) ROOCH_2X , (iii) PPA, (v) POCl₃.

was washed well with water and crystallised from DMF-ethanol to yield dark yellow crystals (5 g, 50%), m.p. 245° (Found: N, 22.16; S, 12.83. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N}_4\text{OSCl}$ requires: N, 22.00; S, 12.57%); ν_{max} 770 (1,2,3-trisubstituted-benzene ring), 1 145 (C=S), 1 610 (C=N), 1 695 (C=O), 3 140, 3 350 and 3 458 cm^{-1} (NH, NH₂).

6-Chloro-5H-2,3-dihydro [1,2,4]triazino [5,6-b]indole-3-thione (2): A mixture of 7-chloroisatin-3-thiosemicarbazone (1; 7.62 g, 0.03 mol) in aqueous KOH (4%; 200 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the insoluble material was removed by filtration. The filtrate on neutralisation with dilute HCl gave yellow solid which was washed well with water and crystallised from DMF-H₂O mixture to furnish light yellow crystals (6 g, 84.7%), m.p. 235° (Found: N, 23.38; S, 13.92. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_5\text{N}_4\text{SCl}$ requires: N, 23.68; S, 13.53%); ν_{max} 775 (1,2,3-trisubstituted benzene ring), 1 140 (C=S), 1 572 (C-N), 1 620 (C=N) and 3 300 cm^{-1} (NH).

5H-3-p-Chlorophenacylthio-6 chloro[1,2,4]triazino [5,6-b]indole (3a, R=p-Cl-C₆H₄): A mixture of 2 (1.18 g, 0.005 mol) and p-chlorophenacyl bromide (1.17 g, 0.005 mol) in DMF (40 ml) was refluxed on a heating mantle for 4 h, then cooled and neutralised with potassium carbonate solution. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from DMF giving brown coloured crystals (1.52 g, 65%), m.p. 120° (Found: N, 13.87; S, 7.75. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{OSCl}_2$ requires: N, 14.39; S, 8.22%); ν_{max} 770 (1,2,3-trisubstituted benzene ring), 825 (1,4-disubstituted benzene ring), 1 575 (C-N), 1 620 (C=N), 1 675 (C=O) and 3 325 cm^{-1} (NH).

3-p-Chlorophenyl-9-chlorothiazolo[3',2':2,3][1,2,4]triazino[5,6-b]indole (4a, R=p-Cl-C₆H₄): The

ketone (3a; 1.0 g) in a mixture of orthophosphoric acid (3.0 ml) and phosphorous pentoxide (4.0 g) was heated on an oil-bath at 150° for 4 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled to room temperature, poured into water and neutralised with aqueous potassium carbonate solution. The resulting solid was washed well with water and crystallised from DMF giving brown black granular crystals (0.55 g, 58.50%), m.p. 232° (Found: C, 55.21; H, 2.5; N, 14.68; S, 8.18. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{SCl}_2$ requires: C, 54.98; H, 2.15; N, 15.09; S, 8.62%); ν_{max} 780 (1,2,3-trisubstituted benzene ring), 830 (1,4-disubstituted benzene ring), 1 515 (C-N), 1 625 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (TFA) 7.80 (1H, s, C₉-H) and 7.63-8.22 (7H, m, ArH).

The physical data of the ketones (3) and thiazolo-triazinoindoles (4) are given in the Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3 AND 4*

Compd. no.	R	M.p. °C	Mol. formula
3b	p-Br-C ₆ H ₄	141	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₄ OSBrCl
3c	p-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	198	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₄ SOCl
3d	p-C ₆ H ₅ -O-C ₆ H ₄	186	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ ON ₄ SOCl
4b	p-Br-C ₆ H ₄	>250	C ₁₇ H ₈ N ₄ SBrCl
4c	p-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	>250	C ₁₇ H ₈ O ₂ N ₄ SOCl
4d	p-C ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄	>250	C ₂₃ H ₁₂ N ₄ SOCl

*All compounds gave satisfactory N and S analyses.

7-Chloroisatin-3-(4-p-chlorophenyl-2-thiazolyl)hydrazone hydrobromide (5a; R=p-Cl-C₆H₄): A mixture of 1 (1.27 g, 0.005 mol) and p-chlorophenacyl bromide (1.17 g, 0.005 mol) in anhydrous ethanol (25 ml) and DMF (25 ml) was refluxed on a heating mantle for 3 h when yellow coloured solid separated out. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and the solid filtered, washed

well with water and crystallised from DMF to give yellow coloured, solid (1.21 g, 52.6%), m.p. 250° (Found: N, 13.96; S, 8.09. $C_{17}H_{11}N_4OSBrCl_2$ requires: N, 14.39; S, 8.44%); ν_{max} 775 (1,2,3-trisubstituted benzene ring), 825 (1,4-disubstituted benzene ring), 1540 (C-N), 1610, 1625 (C=N), 3030 (aromatic C-H) and 3150 cm^{-1} (NH).

1-(p-Chlorophenyl)-9-chlorothiazolo[2',3':3,4][1,2,4]triazino[5,6-b]indole (6a; R=p-Cl-C₆H₄): Compound 5a (1.0 g) in POCl₃ (10.0 ml) was heated in an oil-bath at 125° for 3 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled to room temperature, poured into cold water and neutralised with K₂CO₃ solution. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from DMF to furnish greenish yellow crystals (0.6 g, 62.5%), m.p. 118° (Found: C, 54.74; H, 2.67; N, 15.18; S, 9.10. $C_{17}H_8N_4SCl_2$ requires: C, 54.98; H, 2.15; N, 15.09; S, 8.62%); ν_{max} 775 (1,2,3-trisubstituted benzene ring), 850 (1,4-disubstituted benzene ring), 1535 (C-N), 1630 (C=N); δ (TFA) 7.75 (1H, s, C₂-H) and 7.50-7.82 (7H, m, ArH).

The physical data of the ketones (5) and thiazotriazinoindoles (6) are recorded in the Table 2.

Antimicrobial activities: The compounds 4 (R=p-Br-C₆H₄) and 6 (R=p-Br-C₆H₄) were evaluated for their antimicrobial activity against gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*), gram-negative (*Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*)

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 5 AND 6*

Compd. no.	R	M.p. °C	Mol. formula
5b	C ₆ H ₅	>250	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ ON ₄ SCl ₂
5c	p-Br-C ₆ H ₄	>250	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₄ OSBr ₂ Cl
5d	p-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	>250	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ SClBr
5e	p-C ₆ H ₄ -C ₆ H ₄	>250	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ SBrClO
6b	C ₆ H ₅	>250	C ₁₇ H ₉ N ₄ SCl
6c	p-Br-C ₆ H ₄	250	C ₁₇ H ₉ N ₄ SBrCl
6d	p-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	>250	C ₁₇ H ₉ N ₄ O ₂ SCl
6e	p-C ₆ H ₄ -C ₆ H ₄	232	C ₂₃ H ₁₂ N ₄ SCl

*All compounds gave satisfactory N and S analyses.

bacteria and fungus (*Candida albicans*) by neat samples and serial plate dilution method⁴.

Both the systems exhibit the same type of activity. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of the compound 4 (R=p-Br-C₆H₄) and 6 (R=p-Br-C₆H₄) were found to be 250 and 500 $\mu g ml^{-1}$ against *E. coli* and *C. albicans*, respectively.

References

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